

ACCOUNTING FOR SHEARED TEXTILE COMPOSITE UNIT CELL PROPERTIES IN MACRO SCALE FE SIMULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

For woven materials, shear is the dominant deformation mechanism in the forming process, as the planar fabric conforms to the 3D shape of the final part. The change in fabric geometry, due to the shearing of the fabric, is carried through the consolidation process and is locked into the finished, cured, composite component. Consequently, the local material behaviour is modified, which is typically not taken into account in mechanical performance simulations at component level. Including the effect of shear may improve the accuracy of macro-scale simulations.

This paper focuses on the extraction of homogenized mechanical properties from sheared unit cell models, and the use of these properties in macro-scale component models. Analysis is performed to include deformation, arising during the forming procedure, in the models.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shear is the dominant deformation mechanism in the forming process, as the 2D fabric conforms to 3D shapes [1][2]. This change in fabric geometry is carried through the consolidation process and is locked into the finished, cured, composite component.

For a 2D woven composite, it is the warp and weft directions that primarily determine the material's anisotropic behaviour. As a unit cell shears, the weft and warp tows rotate away from the original orthogonal axes, which has a significant effect on its directional properties.

The effect of shear is not generally taken into account in mechanical performance simulations at component level, especially in industrial applications. Including localised shear behaviour may remove a substantial error in stiffness and strength estimations and improves the accuracy of macro-scale simulations.

Through the development of a robust virtual tool, it is possible to identify mechanical property change for a given shear angle. From forming simulations developed in [3][4], we can identify where shear occurs on a complex part and modify these local regions to update the mechanical properties, through an automatic mapping technique.

2 WORK FLOW

Previous work focused on obtaining the new directional properties of a sheared unit cell [5]. This paper now focuses on mapping of the local shear properties obtained onto the component level FE mesh and its use in mechanical performance simulations. This process can be divided into three stages as shown in Figure 1:

1. Extract fibre directions from forming simulation. Subsequently the shear angle and unit cell rotation are obtained.
2. Identify material properties for the respective shear angles.
3. Map shear distribution and unit cell rotation onto component mechanical performance model mesh and assign respective material properties to local regions.

Figure 1: Work flow chart for the whole project. Blue boxes show the previous work done in [5] and pink covers the work done in this paper. The corresponding paper sections are also referenced.

3 HOMOGENISED UNITCELL DIRECTIONAL PROPERTIES

For a balanced weave, as the warp and weft yarn rotate towards each other, they are no longer orthogonal. However, the bisector of the warp and weft directions remain orthogonal regardless of the shear angle [6][7]. Such orthogonality can be particularly relevant for instances when properties can be only represented by a set of engineering constants and when orthotropy remains the sensible approximation.

In the previous work [5], a major concept developed was the use of primary axis called “shear orientation”. This allows the tracking of the unit cell rotation during the forming simulation. In this work, the E22’ direction is chosen to be the shear orientation, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Properties of an unsheared and sheared unit cell, where E_{22}' is the chosen shear orientation, which is tracked during forming simulations, shown as red arrow. [5]

As a highly anisotropic material, the mechanical properties in all the in-plane directions differs significantly, as shown on the polar plot in Figure 3. The shape of the plot also stresses the importance of choosing the most representative direction to describe the mechanical properties for this material.

Young's modulus for unit cell with different shear angles in polar coordinates (GPa)

Figure 3: Stiffness values for all the directions in the polar coordinate system; for unit cell with 4 shear angles (0, 10, 20, and 30 degrees shear angle). Homogenisation method used from [8][9]. Shear orientation is shown as black vertical arrow which is tracked in the forming simulation.

Figure 3 showed the expected behaviour; the higher the shear angle, the more the yarns skew towards the shear orientation axis, hence the higher stiffness. The opposite occurs for the transverse direction. Moreover, as the shear angle becomes higher, the differences in Young's modulus increases exponentially in the direction of shear orientation, as shown in Figure 4. FE analysts may use the look-up graph in Figure 4 to quickly estimate the corresponding mechanical property change for any shear angle.

Figure 4: Graph of input stiffness value for various shear angles at the direction of the shear orientation (E_{22}' axis).

4 IMPLEMENTATION OF UNIT CELL PROPERTIES IN MACRO SCALE SIMULATIONS

To implement the unit cell properties into the macro-scale shell model, one must first perform a forming simulation to identify the shear angle and unit cell rotation, through a modification of the Abaqus VUMAT [3][4]. As an example, we choose the macro scale part to be an automotive floor panel sub-component, as shown in Figure 5. This is a good representative case as it contains concave and convex features for high localised shear angle to occur.

Figure 5 : (a) Forming simulation of an automotive floor panel sub-component. Contours show the shear angle distribution in radians. Note that the tool used for forming simulation is bigger than the desired part to match with real life practices. (b) Plot showing the shear angle in degrees and the 2D shear orientation distribution. For negative shear angles, the material properties in the transverse direction of the shear orientation are used.

From Figure 5, the regions with high shear angles only occur at complex geometry locations, where the local fibres rotate due to the double curvature.

Figure 6: Mechanical performance simulation mesh where the shear properties are mapped onto.

Once the shear angle and shear orientation data are obtained, it is required to map these data onto the desired macro scale shell model mesh and to assign their local material data. Figure 6 shows an example mesh, which can be created independently in the FE analysis process. A spatial hashing technique [10] is implemented to reduce the run time during the mapping process.

5 RESULTS

A unique material and orientation are written for every element in the shell model. Where the element orientation corresponds to the shear orientation. Mechanical simulation is then performed to examine the effect of the updated properties, using the model and boundary conditions shown in Figure 7. Another model, which did not consider yarn rotation and shear angle, but instead used baseline woven composite properties, was also created to compare differences in results.

Figure 7: Boundary “ENCASTRE” and 4 point-loads applied to the shell model.

Figure 8: In-plane strain plots from models with (a) shear angle and orientation considered. (b) Without shear angle and orientation. Comparing element 7497 in both cases, when taking shear into consideration, the strain has increased by 23.7%.

Figure 8 shows a comparison of strain distribution for a model with shear angle and unit cell rotation considered, to a baseline model without shear being considered. The figure also looks up closely the region of our interest, where high shear angle occurs, as shown in Figure 9. A substantial difference in strain is found within this region for the two models.

Figure 9: The equivalent region to compare with: (a) Shear angle distribution from forming simulation. (b) Shear angle and orientation as mapped to target mesh.

5 DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

The relatively simple linear elastic analysis performed on the two models, one considering the forming process and one not, showed there are some differences between the two results. The region of interest in Figure 8 and Figure 9 shows that the shear angle does affect local element behavior and the difference in maximum strain can be as high as 20%. Currently only the stiffness of the structure has been assessed, considering the shear deformation in failure models is expected to have a greater effect on the model results, helping to predict the failure zones more accurately. Experimental work will be done to validate the FE simulations.

In this paper a methodology is proposed for taking account of shear angle in macro scale FE simulations. More work is required to assess the accuracy and effectiveness of this method.

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